

The “Ville Verte”: rethinking city landscape

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Within the development of twentieth-century city, architects and town planners have conceived the presence of green features under two facets: on one side they are tools to ameliorate the spatial quality of neighbourhoods and specific areas, on the other side they are strategic elements by which it is possible to elaborate a profound re-thinking of the identity of the modern city in itself.

The end of nineteenth century saw the birth of Ebenezer Howard’s theory whose results produced the garden cities of early twentieth century. By means of the “harmonious wedding” between city and country the garden city was to become a real alternative to the unresolved growth of the towns produced by the industrial revolution. More than two decades after Howard’s experiments, Le Corbusier was the first to elaborate a new urban model, which could represent a strategic alternative to the existing city, though still influenced by Howard’s theory. Through his design Le Corbusier was able to re-think the role of green features within the built areas; he conceived naturalness as a tool to reshape the urban environment. In the corbusian vision, the modern city was to be planned in all its aspects, elements and functions; within them a diffused green network would play the role of connective tissue, to recall the metaphor of the human organism.

Le Corbusier was deeply convinced that any solution to the crisis of the city would necessitate of a pact between architecture and nature. By 1922 his proposal for the “Ville contemporaine pour 3 millions d’habitants” was fully formulated. The “Ville contemporaine” is a city of skyscrapers two hundred meters high, where the geometric forms of the

buildings emerge from an uninterrupted green plane shaped as a landscape garden, crossed by a grid of elevated highways. The green spaces, which penetrate the interstices among the buildings become the tool to create the relationship among the urban parts; they allow building a new environmental unity under the mark of the nature into the city.

In the following years Le Corbusier developed his thoughts in a new project of ideal city, to which he gave publicity at the III CIAM Conference, held in Brussels in November 1930. Epitomized “Ville Radieuse”, it is a proposal for a green city with high residential density. On the drawings, which represent his project, Le Corbusier introduced the new slogan, which will characterise his new city: “Ville Verte”.

The uninterrupted green plane becomes the continuous surface, which holds large residential blocks, while strips of parklands separate the functional parts of the city.

The strongly fascinating image of the corbusian city differs from all the others anti-urban ideologies of his time. His project clearly shows that the new green city is not a rarefied city, with few inhabitants dispersed into green areas. It is a large metropolis for vast quantity of inhabitants with a density, which could be even bigger than the one in the existing city. Nature, sunlight, and air break into the urban scene.

These aspects redefine the characters of the new modern planning, though their enforcement sees a random diffusion and some of the most brilliant results are achieved quite far away from Europe, its land of origin.

Le Corbusier himself has had one single opportunity to apply his principles at large scale; this is the case of Chandigarh, the new capital of Punjab in north-eastern India, whose plan Le Corbusier designed from 1951 onward, explicitly referring to the “Ville Radieuse” model, the city of modern times. Many scholars have discussed the qualities and the deficiencies of Le Corbusier’s design for the three major buildings, which form the “Capitol” of the new city. Instead, very few have given relevance to the fact that Chandigarh offers a unique example of a green city of the twentieth century.

Recalling the masterly designed plan of the seven V, a hierarchical grid of green spaces intersects the city. The Leisure Valley Park, a major fluvial park crosses the entire urban area; a system of linear green spaces, equipped with school facilities and sport fields, goes across the residential sectors; parkways and green streets inside the sectors mark this urban strategy. They set up the backbone of the complete urban structure. Furthermore they connect the structure of the city to the morphological pat-

tern of the encircling rural territory by means of an intersecting linear system of water and green features and the large use of tree-plantations and parks.

In his plan Le Corbusier introduced elements taken from nature as architectonic material with the objective to give shape to a the new urban landscape. He has entered each detail of this global planning and studied the relationships between vegetation and form and type of tree-plantation.

Their selection received much accuracy. In 1953, with the birth of the "Landscape Advisory Committee" Le Corbusier began to collaborate with a group of experts, and among them with doctor M.S. Randhawa, a renown Indian botanist who assisted him with the choices and the modalities of grouping.

A similar concept of fusion between the characters of the cityscape and those of the natural space has inspired some projects developed in Brazil. It was applied by Costa and Niemeyer in their plan for Brasilia (1956 onward) and was the matrix in the planning of the Flamengo Park along the edges of Guanabara Bay, in Rio de Janeiro. This magnificent waterfront was built between 1954 and 1964 by a group of designers led by Mario Carlota de Macedo Soares; Roberto Burle Marx designed the landscaping. Gardens, beaches, sport fields, public buildings, such as the Museum of Modern Art, a major urban highway, all fused in a planned continuum make this area a remarkable example of a new town heart conceived within the theory of the modern movement city.

In Europe, the accomplishment of Le Corbusier's principles has mainly resulted in the diffusion of planning techniques based on the introduction of parameters which regulate the criteria for the exploitation of the ground and the relationship between built space and green space. Town-planners call these parameters planning standards. In many countries the introduction of these standards has been the only guarantee of a diffuse presence of green spaces inside the new expansion areas.

This process did not led to the realization of the "Ville Radieuse" rather to a partial surrogate. In the years after the end of Second World War and mainly in the countries where the modern movement has had a strong impact, many new neighbourhoods and satellite towns were designed showing a high percentage of diffused green features.

Convincing projects of this highly rationalized planning featuring a strong presence of diffused green spaces can be found, for example, in the Netherlands. The rationalized planning of the territory according to diverse scales has produced very remarkable results and true manifestos of a new environmental aesthetic. In the small rural town of Nagele, build at the end of the '40s on the new

reclaimed land of the Noord-Oostpolder, the functionalist architects of the groups "de 8" and "Opbouw" have achieved paradigmatic results. In Nagele the model of the functional planning has been integrated into the historical tradition of the construction of the rural landscape. The architects were able to develop a project, which ended in the affirmation of a new environment with no breaks between architecture and man-made nature, between solid built and green built. The global rationality of the construction assumes aesthetic values and meanings.

From the '70s onward this model of global planning passed through a crisis, whose reasons are various. On one hand, the focus on large-scale design has diminished the discourse on the quality of architecture per se and deprived the value of the urban environment. On the other hand, the attention of architects and planners has drastically moved from the new city to the rehabilitation of the existing districts.

This retreat toward the built fabric of the historical city finds a well-known example in Barcelona. The Catalan designers have put in practice a strategy of urban renewal which has put less efforts directed to the planning of the city as global entity. Rather, they have privileged a leopard skin strategy, selecting single interventions and acting on specific strong knots, which would originate a process of transformation and renewal of the already existing city. The results are of great interest, though they seem to weak the significance of the integration between architectonic construction and nature so strongly evoked by Le Corbusier's models. Instead, they seem inspired by nineteenth-century concepts, which go back to Haussmann and his Parisian plan, and to the principles of aesthetic and hygienic betterment achieved through inserting green spaces and tree-plantations along the streets of the city.

Nevertheless Barcelona has become an exemplary case study. The Catalan architects have proved that it was still possible to include green elements within the existing urban fabric even when it seemed that no empty spaces were available. As a consequence these new green spaces have become effective tools of the municipal policy toward urban renewal.

In more recent years, the corbusian principle of ample natural spaces integrated within the urban environment is regaining a certain vitality. This change of approach has proved to be fruitful under various aspects. The technological developments are indeed offering to architects and planners the chance for a new interpretation of those visionary models. By the same token a widely spread critical concern toward urban environments in which all traces of naturalness have been cancelled has favoured the conception of new buildings where green spaces, vegeta-

tion and trees are not decorative accessories applied to architecture. They join architecture in a way that eliminates the distinction between landscape and building as separate entities. The improvement of the technical know-how has facilitated the infilling of large green spaces inside or on the roof of existing buildings, transforming the construction into a hybrid between building and green features.

At the end of the '60s a pioneering example of integrating a residential complex into a semi-public park, covering the entire building, was designed by Roberto Gabetti and Aimaro Oreglia d'Isola, with Luciano Re at Ivrea (Italy). The half-circle shaped "Unità residenziale ovest", promoted by Olivetti shows a conscious approach of the designers toward the encircling natural environment, blending the building with the park.

In the '70s another innovative example was offered by Hans Hollein, who designed the Abeitberg Museum in Mönchengladbach, Germany. Here the museum and the public garden become a new unity significantly conceived. The whole building smoothly lies down along the slope of a hill. At the bottom is the public garden, at the top the museum entrance, which is the only piece where the architecture gains its authority. In between the two entities --nature and architecture, the garden and the museum— are intertwined. The contamination is emphasised by the substance given to the design of the contour lines of the hill, creating an imaginary landscape both artificial and natural. The garden extends upon the museum building that develops underneath. Therefore the whole roof surface is left free to become the public garden. The light penetrates the museum rooms through large domed windows. The process of contamination is made explicit by the way of the global composition.

In the Palais Omnisport, a sport palace built in Paris between 1979 and 1983, and designed by M.Andrault, P.Parat, A.Guvan, the external walls have been completely greenified to simulate vertical lawns. This project goes far beyond the search for a new technological skill. It is rather a new way of conceiving the landscape design. In fact the Palais Omnisport is the terminal point of the new public Parc de Bercy. It offers to the green feature of the park a three-dimensional connotation. Even more it has a strong iconic meaning in representing the possibility for the green feature of breaking the closed boundaries of the park, and starting attacking the built city.

In the campus of Delft university in the Netherlands, the architect group Mecanoo has proposed a similar solution. The green space surrounds the building of the new library and climbs its roof. The building appears as generated from the ground in a strong symbiosis between earth and sky and with

the elements that constitute the surrounding urban landscape. The internal space gives a deep sense of protection and tranquillity to the users, mostly due to the strong naturalness of the architecture.

Quite opposite in its features the Umeda skyscraper in Osaka seems to celebrate the myth of the most advanced technologies, a recurrent issue in contemporary Japanese culture. Unexpectedly the building raises from a large garden underneath, which is the replica of a wooden environment with tall trees, intersected by clear streams. In this case the technological achievements and the essence of the primeval nature are deeply intertwined.

The Jardin Atlantique in Paris offers a series of different environments: forest trees, playgrounds, and open lawns. The appearance is very much close to the many public gardens of the recent years. Yet what is exceptional in this case is the site, the location of the garden. The Jardin Atlantique is indeed realised upon the extended canopy that covers the railroad tracks of the Montparnasse station. The two and half hectares of the Jardin Atlantique are a hanging garden, more than twenty meters high, over the tracks the fast trains to the Atlantic coast are leaving from. The garden in itself, conceived as a sequence of quite different areas, embodies the idea of the travel. The many different species that are included are closely related to the coastal environment of the Atlantic Ocean, the final destination of all the trains leaving the station underneath the garden.

The following is another project realized in Paris. A dismissed train track, which reached the edge of the city centre at Place de la Bastille, has been transformed in a green promenade, the Promenade Plantée. What is exceptional in this case, beside the length of five kilometres, is the location of the promenade in relationship to the street section. The train track run on a high viaduct supported by brick arches; the Promenade Plantée runs at the same level, which is the height of the upper floors of the buildings or of the roofs. It even extends its course into small gardens, which have been realized on the top floors of pre-existing multi-storey buildings.

In Stuttgart, Germany, a new plan for the city centre is presently facing its initial phase. The plan's goal is to redesign the core of the city around the central station designed by Paul Bonatz in the '30s as a terminal station. The most innovative and qualifying feature of the plan is given by the relocation of the tracks' network under the street level, which will also convert the station into a transit station. This transformation allows the clearance of large areas in the most inner part of the city; these areas, where new buildings will also arise, will be mainly treated as open green spaces, which will create the new centre of the city of the future.

The concept of the interplay between architecture and green elements does no longer concern one individual garden or one individual building; this kind of contamination extends its effects to the whole urban environment. In this specific case, taking advantage from the possibilities derived from the relocation of transport infrastructures under the soil, unexpected perspectives are open to a creative use.

All these examples show a high degree of invention with the objective of introducing green spaces in those neighbourhoods where the lack of free ground would make impossible to realize new gardens. What was few years ago the future has become the daily reality. At the present the deteriorated urban environment can be effectively reshaped through the insert of new connecting elements and green channels.

Other interesting examples of this rethinking of the urban environment in the direction of major care for naturalness are more and more frequently offered by cities grown along river banks.

In New York city, the whole western edge of downtown Manhattan has been totally reconfigured by inserting a linear park, the Battery Park, which skirts the urban fabric along the Hudson river. In this case, the area is the result of the reclamation project of part of the bay. The linear park meanders inside the very dense construction of the financial district and breaks the continuity of the riverfront creating small harbours and green squares.

Similarly in Tokyo, the reclamation of one part of the bay area where the old harbour was located, has resulted in the construction of a new neighbourhood, called Tokyo Bay. The complexity of existing urban fabric, crossed by large infrastructures, is retained in the new planning. The lovely beach, which forms the edge of the new park, can induce to an optimistic sense of naiveté. In fact the whole Tokyo Bay is a new landscape integrally invented in the heart of the metropolis. It is the result of a new vision, which mixes up the rules of the traditional urban planning. Looking around one is attracted by apparently natural features, which intertwined with highly sophisticated buildings and technological infrastructures.

The traditional concept of the green space within city, initially expressed by the nineteenth-century concept of public garden, is slowly losing its authority. It is vanishing at the advantage of a complex network of green fragments, which are constantly eroding the concrete materiality of the existing city, slowly creeping into its anfractuosités, rising on the roofs, and occupying its open spaces and emptiness.

Recently, in Italy, a successful series of commercial TV spots, advertising naturally produced cookies, showed how historical cities would look like, if open spaces, for instance worldwide known squares,

would be filled up with wheat fields and more generically with fragments of countryside. Though advertising and TV play with virtual urban landscapes, these evocative images could show, even if from the point of view of the commercial media, a new operational approach to landscape architecture. Nowadays the process of beautification of the city could enlarge its boundaries to the point of considering among its task the redesign of the whole urban environment as a new entity.

The "Ville Verte", conceived by Le Corbusier as a concrete alternative to the existing city, has been probably dismissed too quickly under the pressure of the technocratic planning of the '60s and early '70s, simplistically enlisted among the utopias of the past. The values of that conception have been recently revitalized by some successful projects and, not least, by the present ecological issues. It is very much so that these values will eventually become the model of the new city of the twenty-first century.

Fig. 1 – Le Corbusier, "La Ville Verte", from *Précision sur un état présent de l'architecture et de l'urbanisme*, Paris 1930.

Fig. 2 – The new village of Nagele in North-east polder (the Netherlands). The groups of architects "de 8" and "Opbouw" designed the village in 1947; the construction started in 1954. The design of the site shows a remarkable arrangement of natural and artificial features.

Fig. 3 – View of the Leisure Valley Park in Chandigarh, the main linear park crossing the city.

Fig. 4 – R. Burle-Marx, Flamengo Park, Rio de Janeiro 1952-1964. View of the gardens of the Museum of Modern Art.

Fig. 5 – D. Freixes, V. Miranda, Clot Park, Barcelona 1982-1986. During the '80s public gardens became tools to rethink the urban scene in Barcelona.

Fig. 6 – S.Child, S.Eckstut, Battery Park, Downtown Manhattan, New York 1982-1988. The garden, reclaimed from the Hudson river, reshaped the waterfront of the Financial District.

Fig. 7 – R.Gabetti, A.Oreglia d'Isola, with L.Re, "Unità residenziale Ovest", Ivrea (Italy) 1968-1971. The project is a pioneering example of overlapping of a park and a residential complex.

Fig. 8 – H.Hollein, Abeitberg Museum, Mönchengladbach 1972-1982. View of the garden superimposed to the roof of the museum

Fig. 9 – F. Brun, M. Péna, Jardin Atlantique, Paris 1992-1994. The garden hangs over the tracks of the Montparnasse station.

Fig. 10 – Pantheon square in Rome transformed as a green grass field in a TV advertisement.

Fig. 11 – Mecanoo, Library of Delft University of Technology, Delft 1997. The slope covering the building becomes part of the surrounding green public square.

KEYWORDS

Landscape, Le Corbusier, Public parks, Open Space, Urban environment

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